

species. That makes understanding how the community behaves important. When a particular pest species is affected by specific interventions, such as planting a resistant variety or applying selective insecticides, the community structure may also be affected. When one component is reduced, other species living in the same niche may become more dominant with the removal of competition. The predator guild may be reduced, causing abnormal increases in other pest species.

We studied the dynamic developments in an irrigated rice arthropod community during the dry and wet seasons. In both trials, 20 samples from an insecticide-free, 25- × 100-m² plot at the IRRI farm were collected at 3-d intervals using the CO₂NE sampler in the dry season and using a D-Vac sampling machine in the wet season.

Because populations are indefinitely large, and it is not possible to collect, count, and identify all individuals in a community, the sample was taken to represent members of the community.

Arthropods were sorted into species and counted. Hemipterans predominated in all samples. Species from two guilds—phytophages and predators—were found. The phytophages were composed primarily of pest species, such as leafhoppers and planthoppers. The predators consisted of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and *Microvelia atrolineata* (Fig. 1). Other groups of arthropods, in relatively low numbers, were spiders, coleopterans, hymenopterans, and dipterans.

The Shannon Wiener Index was used to describe species diversity:

$$H(s) = -\sum_{i=1}^s p_i \log p_i$$

where s is the number of species and p_i is the proportional abundance of the i^{th} species.

We calculated $H(s)$ and its standard error for each sampling date. Species diversity increased with crop age to about 3 wk after transplanting, then remained relatively unchanged until harvest (Fig. 2).

The plateau value of $H(s)$ varied

Fig. 1. Arthropods in 2 crops of IR66 grown under submerged conditions. IRRI farm, 1988.

Fig. 2. Shannon-Wiener diversity index in 2 crops of IR66 grown under submerged conditions. IRRI farm, 1988.

between 1.75 and 2.25, implying that arthropod diversity was determined by 6 to 9 species. Those species are ranked by abundance:

Feb-May 1988 (dry season)

Micronecta sp. 1
Microvelia atrolineata
Nephotettix virescens
Microvelia vittigera
Cyrtorhinus lividipennis
Tetragnatha sp. 1
Callitrichia formosana
Dystiscus sp. 1
Nephotettix nigropictus
Lycosa pseudoannulata

Jul-Oct 1988 (wet season)

Nephotettix virescens
Microvelia atrolineata
Sogatella furcifera
Cyrtorhinus lividipennis
Lycosa pseudoannulata
Nephotettix nigropictus
Gryllid sp. 1
Callitrichia formosana
Gonatocerus sp. 1
Microvelia vittigera □

A method for collecting leafroller (LF) eggs on nonplant substrates

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Methods for collecting LF eggs to use in experiments and varietal screening involve caging field-collected or laboratory-reared moths on potted 30- to 40-d-old rice plants. Plants with eggs are removed daily and incubated until the larvae hatch.

The process is cumbersome, requires large cages and insectary space, and inefficient. Most eggs are laid on the walls of the cages.

We developed a new oviposition cage in which the moths lay their eggs on black cloth. Wire gauze is rolled into a 5-cm-diameter cylinder 10 cm

long. Two 6-cm-diameter petri dishes washed with a layer of moist cotton overlaid with a circular piece of black cotton cloth are fitted onto each end of the wire gauze cylinder with rubber bands (see figure).

Two pairs of moths can be released inside the cage through a hole made in the wire gauze. The hole is closed with a ball of cotton dipped in 25% honey solution.

We kept cages with moths in darkness. Eggs were laid on the black cloth. They were removed daily and the black cloth reused.

The number of eggs laid on cloth and on potted rice plants did not differ (see table). However, when cellulose paper was substituted for black cloth, no eggs were laid.

Hatchability of eggs laid on cloth was >90%. Also, freshly laid eggs are easily counted against the dark background. (No color preference by the

Cage for oviposition of rice LF.

moths is implied.) Eggs collected on a nonplant substrate, such as cloth, are easier to sterilize.

Collecting eggs on cloth would be useful in large-scale rearing of LF and when first-instar larvae are to be infested with minimum handling. This method would be particularly useful where larvae are to be tested in sterile conditions, such as on callus and on artificial diets. The oviposition cage can also be used in assaying various LF

Oviposition of the rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) on rice leaves and nonplant substrates.

Substrate	Eggs/2 females per d (mean ± SE)
On potted IR36 plants in the insectary	56 ± 15
On black cloth in the oviposition cages	63 ± 9

^aAv of 9 replications.

attractants and oviposition stimulants. □

A nuclear polyhedrosis virus from rice skipper

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Rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* (Fabricius) occurs mostly in rainfed rice. It causes damage similar to that from other rice defoliators (armyworms and rice green semiloopers).

We isolated a nuclear polyhedrosis virus (PmNPV) from a rice skipper colony in the greenhouse at IRRI. Virus-infected rice skippers were sluggish, ceased feeding, and died. Cadavers exhibited typical symptoms of virus-killed larvae: black color and liquefied body contents.

We purified the PmNPV by macerating PmNPV-infected rice skipper larvae with 0.1% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) in a glass homogenizer and filtering through four layers of

cheesecloth to remove large particles of insect debris. The filtrate was centrifuged at 100 g (1,000 rpm in Beckman rotor JA-20) for 1 min and the precipitate was discarded.

The supernatant was centrifuged at 2,500 g (6,000 rpm in Beckman rotor JA-20) for 10 min to remove lipid, soluble material, and small contaminants. The pellet was resuspended with 0.1% SDS and the centrifuging cycle repeated three times.

The final pellet was resuspended in a small volume of distilled water and centrifuged on 30-80% (vol/vol) discontinuous glycerol gradients in a Beckman SW-27 swing bucket rotor with a Beckman L8-M ultracentrifuge at 1,500 g or 3,500 rpm for 10 min.

The white virus band was collected, diluted with distilled water, and centrifuged at 2,500 g for 10 min. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet resuspended in distilled water and centrifuged on 25-60% (wt/wt) linear sucrose gradients in a Beckman SW-27 rotor at 1,500 g or 10,000 rpm for 30 min.

The virus band formed was collected

with a pipette, diluted with distilled water, and centrifuged at 2,500 g for 30 min to remove the sucrose. The pellet was suspended in distilled water and stored in a freezer.

The 0.858 ± 0.143 μm polyhedra was somewhat tetragonal (Fig. 1).

The virions in the polyhedra were released by mixing equal volume of PmNPV suspension with 0.1 M NaCO₃ (pH = 10.7) for 60 min at 30 °C. The

1. Electron micrograph of the nuclear polyhedrosis virus from the rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* stained with 2% PTA.